

Average-energy efficient static routing in wireless networks

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Abstract. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) are an important part of data acquisition and transmission in modern industrial processes. Thanks to advancements in electronics, a wireless sensor network can be a cheap and reliable way to measure multiple different values in a given process, such as meteorological or industrial. A WSN consists of multiple nodes, each of which typically has a sensor to measure some part of the process and a module capable of transmitting this data wirelessly to a central base station. Energy efficiency becomes a key part of transmission when the nodes are power-constrained. To improve the efficiency of transmission, messages are usually transmitted over multiple hops in a network. In this paper, we analyze static routing algorithms, where the transmission path do not depend on the current state of the network. We look at different optimization parameters, and give approximations to the ideal solution.

Keywords: IoT; WSN; routing; Wireless Sensor Network; WiFi; routing;

1 Introduction

In the last few years, data acquisition and processing has become a key part of many technological improvements. Areas like process monitoring, predictive modelling and machine learning require substantial amount of data.

Depending on the type of data needed, real-life values must be measured, processed and transmitted, such as in meteorological or industrial use-cases. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) can provide a cost-effective and efficient way to collect significant amount and different types of data. These networks typically consist a central base station, where different measurements are being sent, and a number of sensor nodes. The nodes can measure some local property, and transmit the result through the network.

Due to their usually small footprint and wireless transmission, sensor nodes can be easily deployed in most locations. However, in cases when the electrical energy is expensive or a built-in battery is used, energy-efficiency becomes an important part of network planning. To reduce transmission energy usage, nodes typically send messages over multiple hops through the network.

A number of different routing algorithms have been proposed over the years. These however don't take into account the reliability of wireless transmissions.

When quality of service is required, new algorithms are required to provide energy-efficient communication with the given criteria.

2 Related Works

A number of routing algorithms have been proposed for energy-efficient routing in wireless sensor networks.

LEACH[1] has been suggested for cases where the sensor nodes are closer to each other, and the base station is placed further apart. Under these circumstances, direct communication between nodes and the base station is energy-intensive and should be reduced as much as possible.

To achieve this, clusters are randomly generated in the network, and all messages inside the cluster are collected and transmitted by a single cluster head. The clusters are periodically recreated to avoid exhaustion of a single node. Other variants have been developed that improve the efficiency by changing the cluster head selection algorithm or transmission protocol, such as LEACH-B[2].

PEGASIS[3] is another famous routing algorithm for similar environments (sensor nodes close together and the base station is placed farther away). This is used when only aggravated data are needed at the base station (such as minimum, maximum and average values)

To keep transmissions between nodes fair and evenly distributed, a transmission chain is generated between the nodes. A node is selected as the main transmission node. Every node transmits their aggravated data towards the main node. The main node then transmits the final results to the base station. After this, a new main node is selected along the chain.

Over the years, many routing new and modified routing algorithms have been proposed and implemented. Most of the algorithms calculate the energy needed between transmissions as a function of the distance between nodes and the message size. However, wireless transmissions are inherently unreliable. Energy-efficiency could be further improved if the probability of transmissions were also considered.

In our research, we have developed an energy-efficient dynamic routing algorithm capable of providing this QoS criteria[4]. The main goal of this algorithm is to balance the energy levels of the nodes in the network, so that the batteries deplete around the same time. This maximises the number of messages sent before a single node exhausts itself. Through simulations we have shown that under the same randomly generated networks, our algorithm performed better than either LEACH or PEGASIS.

We have also investigated static routing algorithms in wireless sensor networks [5]. In these algorithms, the transmission routes are pre-computed for a given sensor network layout. The nodes are sending their messages according to these determined paths. However, the proposed static routing algorithm was only capable to minimise the global energy usage during transmissions. Further improvements can be made to increase the number of messages sent during transmission.

3 Model

To evaluate different routing algorithms, we have created a mathematical model. This has already been published in detail[4], but will summarise for this paper.

In our model, we consider the network as a 2D graph. Each node is stationary, meaning that the distances between any two nodes remain constant in time, and each node has a current residual energy level calculated as the starting energy level minus the energy used up forwarding the past packets. Our network consists of a number of nodes and one base station. An example of a randomly generated network can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example WSN. The square represents the base station, while the triangle is a node initiating a transmission.

For modeling the radio propagation, we use the Rayleigh-fading model, which gives us the connection between the transmission energy g_{ij} and the probability of successful packet transfer P_{ij} for nodes i, j , based on [6] in a zero-interference network.

$$g_{ij} = -d_{ij}^2 \frac{\theta \sigma_Z^2}{\ln P_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

where d is the distance between the communicating nodes, θ and σ are the parameters of the environment and communication.

The equation above can be simplified to the following relationship, as the nodes are stationary:

$$g_{ij} \ln P_{ij} = \omega_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_{ij} = -d_{ij}^2 \theta \sigma_Z^2$, is a constant dependent on the distance between the nodes and the parameters of the environment. Because θ and σ_Z^2 are positive values, ω_{ij} will have a negative value. Each packet transmission requires this energy from the the sending node, and in this paper we assume that the receiving node can receive the packet without any energy consumption (in the future work the

reception energy will also be taken into account). In order to ensure a given reliability, we also define the probability P_s as the probability with which the base station must receive the message sent by a node.

4 Maximising the sent message count with static routing

In our previous work, we have looked into the advantages of static routing algorithms, namely the pre-computed transmission routes, easing the computational workload on the nodes. We have also shown that a static routing algorithm can be easily developed with the goal of minimising the global energy usage of the network, useful in circumstances when the energy sources of the nodes are not limited. However, if the energy source is limited, other optimisation must be used to extend the lifetime of the network.

Given a well-defined static routing algorithm and the distribution of the messages being sent over the network, we can calculate how much energy on average a node will use during any message transfer. When the starting energy levels of the nodes are also known, we can also calculate how many messages can be sent on the network a given node exhausts itself. Since the node with the lowest value will determine the lifetime of the network, our goal is to maximise this minimum node message count value in the network.

As of the publication of this paper, we have not found an exact solution to this problem. The complexity of the task comes from the following factors:

- In our model, any two node can communicate with each other, and we have not found many options to substantially reduce the number of possible paths a message can take.
- Supposing that the path of the messages are given, calculating the optimal energy values to be used in the transmissions still remains a hard problem. While an iterative approach can be used that continually increases the minimum node message count, we can not differentiate a local and global optimal solution.
- Due to the probabilistic nature of the communication used, there is a possibility that a message will be lost during a transmission. This must be factored in when calculating the average energy used by a node in a message transfer.

To have a baseline solution that can be compared to other routing algorithms, we have decided to instead solve a simplified and generalised version of this problem. Our goal is to construct the following model as a *mixed-integer convex programming* problem, and solve it using a solver.

5 Optimal path in graph with deterioration

Let us suppose we have a connected graph $G = (V, E)$, where V are the nodes (or vertices) of the graph, and E are the directed edges between the nodes. For every edge $e \in E$, we also have a *deterioration function* $D_e(c)$. Finally, we have list of transmission descriptions with the following values:

- P_t transmission probability: the probability that this transmission is requested next in the network.
- $s, t \in E$: the sending and the receiving nodes in the network respectively.
- D_{lim} deterioration limit.

In this model, our goal is to find a suitable path for every transmission and assign a cost to each edge in the path so that the sum of the deterioration function values remains below the deterioration limit. If multiple solutions exist, we can also look for an optimal solution based on a pre-defined criteria.

In this model, the deterioration function is a monotonic non-increasing function. Along an edge, if we increase the cost used in the transmission, the deterioration will decrease, which in turn may allow us to decrease the cost at another part of the transmission.

For example, a deterioration function could be the transport duration of physical goods. Depending on the characteristics of the transportation used, we can decrease the time it takes to traverse a route at the cost of using more fuel or energy. In this context, our goal could be to minimise the fuel used during the transport while keeping the travel time below a given limit.

Let us now on constructing the mixed-integer convex programming problem. To accomplish this, let us suppose that the deterioration function $D_e(c)$ is convex for each edge. We are first going to provide the necessary constraints. Since the transmission paths are independent of each other, we can focus on a single transmission.

We will first set the constraints so that there will be a path between nodes s and t . This is achieved by introducing the binary variables e_{ij} , representing whether the edge between nodes i and j are used in the transmission. For the starting node s , we have the constraint seen in equation 3.

$$\sum_{\substack{j \\ \{s,j\} \in E}} e_{sj} = 1 \quad (3)$$

This will force that one edge must be selected from the outgoing edges of node s . Similarly, a constraint must be set for the incoming edges of node t , as can be seen in equation 4.

$$\sum_{\substack{i \\ \{i,t\} \in E}} e_{it} = 1 \quad (4)$$

Finally, for every node that is not s or t , we must set that the number of selected incoming and outgoing edges must match. For a given node n , this is accomplished by the equation 5.

$$\sum_{\{i,n\} \in E} e_{in} + \sum_{\{n,j\} \in E} e_{nj} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Equation 6 sets up so that for each node, at most one outgoing edge is selected for the transmission, ensuring that no loops are allowed in the model.

$$\sum_{\{i,n\} \in E} e_{in} \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

Next, we are going to set up the constraints, so that the sum of the deterioration values along the path will be lower than the deterioration limit D_{lim} . To accomplish this, we are going to introduce the continuous variable D_{ij} that represents the deterioration value added by the edge between i and j , and Ds_i that represents the sum deterioration value along the path up to node i .

For each node i that is not t , and for each node j where $\{i, j\} \in E$, we could have the constraint as seen in equation 7.

$$Ds_j \geq (Ds_i + D_{ij})e_{ij} \quad (7)$$

This constraint sets up Ds_j value so that it only has an effect when $e_{ij} = 1$, meaning that the edge is selected for transmission. Unfortunately, this constraint is not permitted, since multiplication of different variables are not allowed in convex programming. However, when at least one of the variables in the multiplication is a binary variable, they can be separated as seen in [7]. This is accomplished in equation 8.

$$\begin{aligned} Ds_j &\geq H_{ij} \\ H_{ij} &\leq D_{lim}e_{ij} \\ H_{ij} &\leq (Ds_i + D_{ij}) \\ H_{ij} &\geq (Ds_i + D_{ij}) - D_{lim}(1 - e_{ij}) \\ H_{ij} &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Note that these constraints will also contain our quality-of-service criteria, namely $Ds_t \leq D_{lim}$

Finally, we introduce the continuous variables c_i , representing the cost incurred by node i . For each node i that is not t , and for each node j where $\{i, j\} \in E$ we set the constraint seen in equation 9.

$$D_{ij} \geq D_{ij}(c_i) \quad (9)$$

Note that further constraints might be required for c_i depending on how $D_{ij}(c_i)$ is defined.

These are the constraints necessary to find a solution in the network for a single transmission. When multiple different transmissions are possible, the same constraints must be generated for each one.

Different goals can be used for finding the optimal solutions among the feasible solutions.

Minimal cost

One goal could be to minimise the sum of costs over every transmission. This is the same as minimising the sum of costs over a single transmission, and so can be separated into distinct optimisation problems. In this case, our goal is specified by equation 10.

$$\text{minimise } \sum_{\substack{i \\ i \neq t}} c_i \quad (10)$$

Minimise maximum of average cost

Another goal could be set so that each node incurs on average the same cost over every transmission. This is accomplished by introducing a new continuous variable C , representing this maximum average cost. To enforce this property, for each node i , we must set equation 11 as constraints, where ${}_t c_i$ represents the cost incurred by node i for transmission t .

$$C \geq \sum_t {}_t c_i P_t \quad (11)$$

Finally, our goal is to minimise the value of C , as can be seen in equation 12.

$$\text{minimise } C \quad (12)$$

This goal can be used in scenarios where the costs are removed from a finite source for each node, and recharging the source is significantly more expensive than the cost. By minimising the maximum average cost, we maximise the number of transmissions in the network before a recharge is needed.

6 Simulations

Using the mixed-integer convex programming model implemented in the previous section, we can approximate a good static routing algorithm in a WSN. To convert our wireless transmission network into a deterioration graph, we must take the absolute value of ω_{ij} and $\ln(P_{ij})$.

Since both of these values are always negative, the original $g_{ij} \ln P_{ij} = \omega_{ij}$ equation will still hold for every solution found with the absolute values. In this case, the deterioration function can be defined as $D_{ij}(c) = |\omega_{ij}|/c$, which is a convex function when $c > 0$.

Table 1: Results of simulations comparing static routing to 2 hop

	Static routing			2-hop routing		
	Sent	Received	Success rate	Sent	Received	Success rate
1	6469	6204	95.9%	6409	6116	95.4%
2	91823	87179	94.9%	44572	42662	95.7%
3	174817	167890	96.0%	122633	119772	97.7%
4	9854	9353	94.9%	9983	9500	95.1%
5	17398	16678	95.9%	16903	16125	95.4%

Note that the deterioration graph is only an approximation to our wireless transfer network, since in the deterioration graph, we suppose that the transmission will always complete over a given path. Meanwhile, with wireless communication, it is possible that a message gets lost during transmission. This will mean that in practice, nodes closer to the base station will have lower average energy usage than the model suggests, since not every message will reach those nodes.

Because the energy sources are finite in our model, we use the goal of minimising the maximum of average cost. This will mean that the nodes send as much message as possible before depleting themselves.

With the given model, we employed a convex programming model solver. This was achieved in MATLAB R2022b with the popular MOSEK 10.1 solver, and CVX, a package for specifying and solving convex programs [8] [9].

After generating multiple different network layout, running the solver and verifying that the provided transmission paths are correct and provide the necessary quality-of-service, we compared it to our 2-hop dynamic routing algorithm introduced in our previous research [4]. The goal of 2-hop routing is to balance the energy levels of the nodes while the transmissions are occurring. This is achieved by node with higher energy levels participating more in a given transmission.

We ran the simulations with five different networks under the same circumstances, with the goal of reaching at least 95% successful transmission rate. The results can be seen in table 1.

As can be seen, static routing usually outperformed 2-hop routing, in some cases with a significant margin as well. In the case when 2-hop routing performed better, further research will be needed to find the exact cause.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we have examined a static routing algorithm in Wireless Sensor Networks. To give an approximate solution, we have also introduced a related problem, which we have named the deterioration graph. We have shown how a mixed-integer convex programming model can be created from the problem definition, and used a solver to find good static routing strategies in five different

randomly generated sensor networks. From the results we concluded that the given static routing algorithm is a viable choice compared to the 2-hop dynamic routing algorithm.

In the future, we would like to develop other static routing algorithms. While the given solution can be used for smaller networks, it does not scale well for larger WSNs. For these cases, a faster approximation could be used, which can then be compared to our complex programming solution for smaller networks.

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